

STRENGTH EVALUATION OF TWILL WOVEN LAMINATED STRUCTURE, CONSIDERING KNEE-POINT

M. Kawaguchi¹, Y. Suzuki¹, K. Tanaka¹ and K. Watanabe¹

¹Department of Biomedical Engineering, Doshisha University
IN115N, 1-3, Miyakodani, Tatara, Kyotanabe-shi, Kyoto, Japan
Email: maskawag@mail.doshisha.ac.jp, web-page: <https://www.doshisha.ac.jp>

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is characterized by high specific strength and stiffness, so applying it to structures is expected to reduce weight. Due to its high formability, woven CFRP is used in various structures. Woven CFRP is so complex to make numerical model due to its dense structure, that homogenization methods, whose modeling cost is expensive, have been used for analysis. On the other hand, modeling with orthogonal anisotropy is considered to be simple and potentially effective in strength evaluation. Currently, strength design and evaluation of structures using CFRP is not widespread enough for industrial companies, so strength evaluation is performed by testing using actual structures. Because of the high cost of tests using actual structures, it is necessary to propose a method for evaluating strength by analysis. In this study, twill woven structure is modeled as a superposition of orthogonal anisotropic materials to simplify its modeling, assuming strength evaluation could be based on the knee point, which is the maximum point that can be approximated linearly in bending behavior. On our analysis, knee point is calculated by assuming that the layer in the laminated structure that reached the breaking strength for each direction of the twill woven prepreg is broken. In this study, two types of laminates are prepared using twill woven prepreps, and the specimens are subjected to three-point bending tests and loading tests of semi-cylindrical structures. In addition, finite element analysis is applied to reproduce these tests in order to verify the validity of the strength evaluation. These results indicate that the strength evaluation of twill woven composite structures can be available considering the strength for the weakest direction of CFRP, using orthogonal anisotropy modeling.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) is characterized by high specific strength and stiffness, so applying it to structures is expected to reduce weight [1-2]. Due to its high formability, woven CFRP is used in various structures such as automobiles, aircraft, and wind power generation blades [3-5]. Woven CFRP is so complex to make numerical model due to its dense structure, that homogenization methods, whose modeling cost is expensive, have been used for analysis. On the other hand, modeling with orthogonal anisotropy is considered to be simple and potentially effective in strength evaluation [6-8].

Currently, strength design and evaluation of structures using CFRP is not widespread enough for industrial companies, so strength evaluation is performed by testing using actual structures [9]. Because of the high cost of tests using actual structures, it is necessary to propose a method for evaluating strength by analysis. In this study, twill woven structure is modeled as a superposition of orthogonal anisotropic materials to simplify its modeling, assuming strength evaluation could be based on the knee point, which is the maximum point that can be approximated linearly in bending behavior. On our analysis, knee point is calculated by assuming that the layer in the laminated structure that reached the breaking strength for each direction of the twill woven prepreg is broken. In this study, two types of laminates are prepared using twill woven prepreps, and the specimens are subjected to three-point bending tests and loading tests of semi-cylindrical structures. In general, knee point strength is said to be 50-60% of breaking strength, so strength evaluation on the knee point is considered effective. In addition, finite element analysis is applied to reproduce these tests in order to verify the validity of the strength evaluation. These results indicate that the strength evaluation of twill woven composite structures can be available considering the strength for the weakest direction of CFRP, using orthogonal anisotropy modeling.

2 STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE SHEET

2.1 Preface

In this study, strength evaluation is focused on knee point. Knee point is the maximum point that can be approximated linearly on the stress-strain diagram, as shown in Fig. 1. The knee point is assumed to be caused by the rupture of the weakest layer of the laminated composite. Tensile strength of the composite sheet before laminate forming is experimentally determined as breaking stress, and the strength is evaluated based on this breaking stress.

Figure 1: Composite sheet tensile test specimen.

2.2 Tensile test

Twill composite sheet of 0.25 mm thickness is used as the test material. The warp direction of twill structure is set at 0° , and the composite sheet is cut at oblique angles of 0° , 45° , and 90° . Test specimens are prepared as shown in the Fig. 2 and aluminum tabs are adhered. Strain gauges are attached to the center, and strain measurements are performed using a measuring device. Uniaxial tensile load is applied using Autograph. Stress-strain diagrams from tensile tests of composite sheets are shown in Fig. 3. The results of breaking stress and modulus of elasticity at oblique angles of 0° , 45° and 90° are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Both the breaking stress and modulus are lowest in the 45° oblique sheet, where the fibers are not aligned.

Figure 2: Composite sheet tensile test specimen.

Figure 3: Stress-strain diagram for tensile testing of composite sheets.

Figure 4: Tensile strength of composite sheets.

Figure 5: Modulus of composite sheets.

2.3 Tensile Analysis

The composite sheet is treated as an approximated model consisting of a unidirectional V material with only the warp component and a unidirectional H material with only the weft component, superimposed as shown in Fig. 6. The longitudinal modulus of elasticity in the L and T directions of the V material is E_{LV} and $E_{TV} (= \alpha E_{LV})$, and the transverse modulus of elasticity in the LT direction is G_{LTV} , where α is the coefficient of elasticity. Similarly, the coefficients of longitudinal elasticity in the L and T directions for the H material are E_{LH} and $E_{TH} (= \alpha E_{LH})$, and the coefficient of transverse elasticity in the LT direction is G_{LTH} . The elastic properties of the twill weave at angles of 0° and 90° are approximated by the superposition of orthogonal anisotropic materials as shown in Equation (1) below. The value of α is set to 0.032 from literature values, and the Poisson's ratio is also set to the general value of 0.3 from the same paper.

$$\begin{aligned} E_0 &= E_{LV} + E_{TH} = E_{LV} + \alpha E_{LH} \\ E_{90} &= E_{LH} + E_{TV} = E_{LH} + \alpha E_{LV} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The theoretical value of the elastic modulus of the twill woven material is also obtained by superposition of orthogonal anisotropic materials. The modulus of elasticity of the XY coordinate system tilted by an angle θ shown in Fig. 7 from the LT coordinate of the unidirectional material is obtained from equation (2) to (4), and the sum of the V and H materials is used to obtain the modulus of elasticity at that angle. ($l = \cos \theta$, $m = \sin \theta$)

$$\frac{1}{E_x} = \frac{1}{E_L} l^4 + \left(\frac{1}{G_{LT}} + \frac{2\nu_{LT}}{E_L} \right) l^2 m^2 + \frac{1}{E_T} m^4 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{1}{E_y} = \frac{1}{E_L} m^4 + \left(\frac{1}{G_{LT}} + \frac{2\nu_{LT}}{E_L} \right) l^2 m^2 + \frac{1}{E_T} l^4 \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{1}{G_{xy}} = 2 \left(\frac{2}{E_L} + \frac{2}{E_T} + \frac{4\nu_{LT}}{E_L} - \frac{1}{G_{LT}} \right) l^2 m^2 + \frac{1}{G_{LT}} (l^4 + m^4) \quad (4)$$

The composite sheet is modeled in FEMAP with NX Nastran as shown in Fig. 7. Shell elements are used and divided into $1\text{mm} \times 1\text{mm}$ rectangular elements. The left end is fully constrained, and the other nodes are free only in the translational XY directions. The load of 1 N is applied to the right end of the model. The physical property values are obtained from Equation 1, and the elastic modulus of the V and H materials are shown in Table 1. Tensile analysis is performed using these physical properties. The distribution of the modulus of elasticity with each angle is shown in Fig. 8. The elastic modulus from the analysis is in qualitative agreement with the theoretical equation. The analytical values are slightly larger than the theoretical values, which may be due to the fact that the V and H materials suppress each other's deformation.

Figure 6: Twill model using orthotropic anisotropy.

Figure 7: Analysis model of bending specimen.

Figure 8: Distribution of elastic modulus at each angle.

Engineering constant		V	H
E_L	[GPa]	57.0	30.8
E_T	[GPa]	1.8	0.9
E_{45}	[GPa]	2.5	1.3
G_{LT}	[GPa]	0.9	0.5

Table 1: Physical properties of V and H materials.

3 STRENGTH OF LAYERED COMPOSITE MATERIAL

3.1 Bending Test

Two types of laminated boards are made by the same composite sheet. Press molding machine (STIP05-05) is used, with molding conditions set at a pressure of 2 MPa, a molding time of 5 minutes, and a molding temperature of 275°C. The laminated board are defined as Type-A [0°/ + 45°/ - 45°/ 90°]_s and Type-B [+ 45°/ 0°/ 90°/ - 45°]_s. Test specimens are cut from the laminated board and three-point bending test is conducted as shown in the Fig. 9. The load-strain diagram obtained from the bending test are shown in the Fig. 10. The knee point loads obtained from the experiments are shown in Table 2. The average load at the knee point was 100 N for Type A and 86 N for Type B.

Figure 9: Diagram of 3-point bending test.

Figure 10: Load-strain curve of 3-point bending tests.

	Type-A[N]	Type-B[N]
No.1	75	108
No.2	107	87
No.3	88	76
No.4	118	62
No.5	113	97
Ave±S.D.	100±18	86±18

Table 2: Knee point load in bending test.

3.2 Finite element analysis

The specimen shown in the Fig. 11 is modeled using stacked layup in FEMAP with NX Nastran. As shown in Fig. 11, the restraint conditions are as follows: the fulcrum of the 3-point bending test is constrained in the direction of translational Y and rotational X and Z direction, while the rest of the specimen is free, that is, in the translational X and Z directions and in the direction of rotation of the Y-axis.

Unit load (1 N) is applied in the negative direction of the Y-axis in the center of the specimen. In this study, the stress is analyzed by 1° with respect to the fiber direction as shown in Fig. 12 for each layer, and the load at which the composite sheet reached the breaking stress at each angle is considered as the knee-point load. The results of tensile tests are used for the rupture stress, and the rupture stress at other angles is assumed to be correlated with the longitudinal modulus of elasticity, resulting in the distribution shown in the Fig. 13. Stress contour plots of the outermost layers of both types are shown in Fig. 14. For both types, the maximum stress occurred at the loaded portion of the specimen. Therefore, the stress at the center of the loaded portion is evaluated.

Figure 11: Analysis model of bending specimen.

Figure 12: Evaluation angle from fiber direction.

Figure 13: Assumed distribution of fracture stress at each angle.

Figure 14: Stress contour of bending test.

3.3 Strength evaluation

In laminated boards, 22.5° pitch direction, where the fibers are not oriented, is considered to be the weakest and most susceptible to fracture, so the stress in 22.5° direction is evaluated. Tables 3 and 4 show the stress in 22.5° direction occurring in each layer of both types. In both types, the stress occurring in Ply 1 and Ply 2 is higher than that in other Plys. In addition, the maximum stress occurred in the 0° material in both types. In this study, stresses are evaluated in 1° increments, and the fracture loads for each direction are determined. Since the stresses in Ply 1 and Ply 2 are higher than those in other plies, resulting in lower fracture loads, Fig 15 shows the distribution of fracture loads for each angle in Ply 1 and Ply 2.

Ply	Angle(°)	Evaluation angle (°)	22.5°directional stress (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
1	0	22.5	1.89	165
2	45	-22.5	0.78	165
3	-45	67.5	0.28	158
4	90	-67.5	0.08	158
5	90	-67.5	-0.08	158
6	-45	67.5	-0.28	158
7	45	-22.5	-0.78	165
8	0	22.5	-1.89	165

Table 3: Analyzed stress of each ply in 22.5° direction (Type-A).

Ply	Angle(°)	Evaluation angle (°)	22.5°directional stress (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
1	45	-22.5	1.36	165
2	0	22.5	1.79	165
3	90	-67.5	0.47	158
4	-45	67.5	0.10	158
5	-45	67.5	-0.10	158
6	90	-67.5	-0.47	158
7	0	22.5	-1.79	165
8	45	-22.5	-1.36	165

Table 4: Analyzed stress of each ply in 22.5° direction (Type-B).

(a) Type-A

(b) Type-B

Figure 15: Distribution of fracture load at each angle in three-point bending analysis.

The knee point load is 87 N (= 165/1.89) for Type A and 92 N (= 165/1.79) for Type B, corresponding to 87% (= 87/100) and 107% (= 92/86) of the experimental values, respectively. The knee point loads in 22.5° direction are plotted in Fig. 15. They locate at about the smallest area of the distribution of the knee point load and the average load of Type-A looks larger than Type-B.

4 STRENGTH OF STRUCTURAL SAMPLE

4.1 Loading test

Laminated boards used in three-point bending tests are also used. Diaphragm molding is used to mold test sample. As shown in the Fig. 16, the laminated plate is heated to 275°C for 500 seconds using an IR oven (DIR631), and the softened laminated plate is pressed into a semicylindrical mold with a diameter of 100 mm and a length of 200 mm. A diaphragm molding machine (MEMBRA6, LEIBROCK CO.) is used to mold the sample with a molding pressure of 0.4 MPa and a vacuum time of 15 seconds to produce a semicylindrical sample. As shown in the figure, the sample is fixed to the fixtures at both ends using epoxy adhesive (Three Bond 2082C), and the test is conducted using a fixture that could apply load only to the central part of the sample shown as Fig. 18. With a test speed of 0.25 mm/min and a support distance of 175 mm, as shown in the Fig. 17. A strain gauge is attached directly below the load

application point to measure the circumferential strain. The load-strain diagram measured by the test is shown in the Fig. 19. Table 5 shows the knee point loads for both types obtained in the test. The average load at the knee point is 1867 N for Type-A and 1269 N for Type-B.

Figure 16: Sample preparation method using diaphragm molding.

Figure 17: Diagram of loading test of structural sample.

Figure 18: Location of load-bearing parts and strain gauge.

Figure 19: Load-strain curve of structural samples.

	Type-A[N]	Type-B[N]
No.1	1764	1462
No.2	1710	1425
No.3	2125	920
Ave±S.D.	1867±226	1269±302

Table 5: Knee point load in Loading tests of structural sample.

4.2 Finite element analysis

The analytical model of the structural sample is created in FEMAP with NX Nastran, using shell rectangular elements with a mesh size of 1 mm. As shown in Fig. 20, a rigid element is used to apply a unit load of 1 N in the negative direction of the Z axis, with the load point as an independent node free only in the translational Z direction and all degrees of freedom dependent on the dependent node on the structural sample side. The support points at the ends are free only in the direction of rotation around the X axis as independent nodes, and the dependent nodes on the structural sample side are subordinated in all degrees of freedom. Stress contour diagrams of the outermost layers of both types are shown in Fig. 21. For both types, there is a tendency for stress concentration at the edge location of loading fixture as Fig. 18. Therefore, stress evaluation is conducted at the stress concentration area for both types. In this study, the stress is transformed by 1° with respect to the fiber direction in each layer, and the load, at which the composite sheet reached breaking stress at each angle, is taken as the knee point load.

Figure 20: Analysis model of structural samples.

Figure 21: Analysis model of structural samples.

4.3 Strength evaluation

Considering that the direction in which the fibers are not oriented is the weakest and most susceptible to breakage, the stress in 67.5° direction is evaluated. Tables 6 and 7 show the stress generated in 67.5° direction for both types. In both cases, the largest value is observed in the outermost layer. The stress obtained from the structural sample analysis is similarly converted 1° at a time from the fiber direction, and the stress generated in each direction is calculated. Similarly, the distribution of angles and fracture loads in Ply1 and Ply2 is shown in Fig. 22.

Ply	Angle(°)	Evaluation angle (°)	67.5°directional stress (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
1	0	67.5	0.076	158
2	45	22.5	0.074	165
3	-45	112.5	0.035	158
4	90	-22.5	0.067	165
5	90	-22.5	0.035	165
6	-45	112.5	-0.001	158
7	45	22.5	-0.025	165
8	0	67.5	-0.021	158

Table 6: Analyzed stress of each ply in 67.5° direction (Type-A).

Ply	Angle(°)	Evaluation angle (°)	67.5°directional stress (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
1	45	22.5	0.085	165
2	0	67.5	0.060	158
3	90	-22.5	0.081	165
4	-45	112.5	0.023	158
5	-45	112.5	0.013	158
6	90	-22.5	0.019	165
7	0	67.5	-0.003	158
8	45	22.5	-0.033	165

Table 7: Analyzed stress of each ply in 67.5° direction (Type-B).

(a)Type-A

(b)Type-B

Figure 22: Distribution of fracture load at each angle in structural sample loading analysis.

In the structural sample analysis, the knee point is defined as the point of failure of the weakest layer, and the minimum fracture load is taken as the knee point load. The knee point loads are 2079 N (= 158/0.076) for Type-A and 1941 N (= 165/0.085) for Type-B, corresponding to 111 % (=2079/1867) and 153 % (= 1941/1269) of the experimental values, respectively. As same as bending test, the knee point loads in the weakest direction are plotted in Fig. 22. The plots of Type-A locate at about the smallest area, and also the plots of Type-B locate at the smallest area.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Tensile tests of composite sheets (CF/PA66 twill weave), flexural tests of laminated composites and loading tests of laminated structure samples, and finite element analysis are conducted to predict the initial failure load using a strength evaluation index based on the knee point of laminated composite material. The following is a summary of the findings.

- The knee point load can be predicted by obtaining the stress in each direction by 22.5° pitch in the analysis of a laminated composite bending specimen. For the laminated composite in this test, the knee point load can be predicted with the error within 13 % for the experimental value.
- The knee point load can be predicted by obtaining the stress in each direction by 22.5° pitch in the structural sample loading analysis. The laminated composite in this test can predict the knee point load with the error within 53% from the experimental value.

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